

Recent Advances in Synthesis and Chemical Biology XXIII

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Organisation: Centre for Synthesis and Chemical Biology

Event Sponsors

Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section, Eli Lilly, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Pfizer, Merck Life Sciences, Mason Technology, Agilent, MSD Ballydine, GPE Scientific and SSPC.

Summary

The 23rd instalment of *Recent Advances in Synthesis and Chemical Biology* was hosted by the Centre for Synthesis and Chemical Biology at UCD Village on Friday 13th December 2024. The programme included five plenary lectures by international research leaders Chris Willis, Bart Jan Ravoo, Kyle Vincent, Hon Lam and Matthew Sigman, as well as eight early-career presentations from various Irish universities. The next CSCB Symposium is scheduled for 12th December 2025.

Attendees

Approximately 160 chemists from academia and industry attended or presented at the meeting.

Target audience: academics, industrialists, postgraduates, ECR (academia/industrial)

Programme

The symposium programme is outlined in Table 1.

Table 1. Programme of Speakers.

Time		
09:00-09:15	Prof. James Sullivan (UCD), Head of School of Chemistry	Opening Remarks
09:15-10:15	<i>Chair: Dr Eoghan McGarrigle (UCD)</i>	
	Prof. Chris Willis University of Bristol	
	The Eli Lilly Lecture: "Exploring and Exploiting Biocatalytic Ring Formation"	
10:15-10:45	Coffee/Tea Break	Poster Session I
10:45-11:45	<i>Chair: Prof. Eoin Scanlan (TCD)</i>	
	Prof. Bart Jan Ravoo University of Münster	
	<i>"Molecular Design of Photoswitches for the Assembly of Responsive Soft Matter"</i>	
11:45-13:00	<i>Chairs: Dr Marina Rubini (UCD) and Prof. Aidan McDonald (TCD)</i>	
	Rachel O'Sullivan (UCD) - <i>The Enantioselective Synthesis of α-Ferrocenyl Tetraarylmethanes;</i> Oscar Kelly (TCD) - <i>Electrostatic Fields induce Accelerated PCET Rates in a Mg-porphyrin P680+ Mimic;</i> Vanessa Becker (UCD) - <i>Carbosulfonylation of Alkenes with Sulfinic Salts;</i> Brian Durkan (RCSI) - <i>Desulfurative fluorination of alkyl phenyl sulfides via bromonium catalysis;</i> Celine Erkey (UCD) - <i>Improvement of Therapeutic Potential via Site-Selective Modification in Human Interferon Gamma;</i> Dr André Campanico (TCD) - <i>Tackling the thiol-ene labelling of enzymes with light- and chemically triggered activity-based probes;</i> Geoffrey Stosse (UCC) - <i>Rhodium-Catalysed Enantioselective 1,4-Conjugate Additions on the Phenyl Backbone of Indole;</i> Dr Marianne Haarr (UCD) - <i>Enzyme-Triggered Reactions for the Construction of Complex Chiral Compounds</i>	
13:00-14:00	Lunch Break	Poster Session II
14:00-15:00	<i>Chair: Prof. Celine Marmion (RCSI, University of Medicine and Health Sciences)</i>	
	Prof. Kyle Vincent University of Oxford	
	<i>"More Sustainable Biotechnology for Chemical Manufacturing: Exploiting Hydrogenases for Biocatalytic Hydrogenation"</i>	
15:00-15:30	Coffee/Tea Break	Poster Session III
15:30-16:30	<i>Chair: Prof. Marcus Baumann (UCD)</i>	
	Prof. Hon Lam University of Nottingham	
	The Thermo Fisher Scientific Lecture: "An Exploration of Morphinan Opioid Chemistry"	
16:30-17:30	<i>Chair: Prof. Pat Guiry (UCD)</i>	
	Prof. Matthew Sigman University of Utah	
	The Pfizer Lecture: "Developing Data Science Tools for Synthetic Chemists"	
17:30	Prof. Pat Guiry , Director, Centre for Synthesis and Chemical Biology	Closing Remarks

Prizes

POSTER PRIZES – awarded to Cian Cloonan (QUB); Rachel Lynch (UCD); Dr Gangireddy Sujeevan Reddy (UCC); Matthew Rowe (TCD).

Figure 1. Professor Pat Guiry with CSCB poster winners: Dr. Gangireddy Sujeevan Reddy (UCC); Matthew Rowe (TCD).

Acknowledgements

The organisers are grateful for the generous support of the sponsors listed above, who have supported the CSCB Symposia over many years.

Previous Events in this Series

This is the 23rd annual CSCB symposium.